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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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THE ROLE OF THE EUROPEAN POLICE OFFICE (EUROPOL) IN THE FIGHT AGAINST ILLEGAL TRAFFICKING NARCOTIC DRUGS

ANNOTATION

The article discusses the main directions, goals and strategic objectives of the monitoring systems and information sources of the European Police Office - Europol (European Police Office). The international scale of drug trafficking and the involvement of an increasing number of states in the global network of illegal transportation routes do not currently allow countries to clearly distinguish between producers of narcotic drugs and their consumers. It is only possible to trace certain trends in the spread of drug trafficking in relation to different continents and analyze them.

Key words: European Police Office (Europol) cooperation, EU, organized crime, international network, implementation of an international regulatory legal act, international structure to neutralize drug trafficking, international drug control, international tactical law enforcement organization.

ЕВРОПА ПОЛИЦИЯ БЎЛИМИНИНГ (EUROPOL), РОЛИ НОҚОНУНИЙ САВДОГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШДА ГИЁХВАНДЛИК ВОСИТАЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада Европа полиция идораси - Европол (European Police Office) мониторинг тизимлари ва ахборот манбаларининг асосий йўналишлари, мақсадлари ва стратегик вазифалари кўриб чиқилган. Гиёхвандлик воситалар савдосининг халқаро миқёси ва кўпайиб бораётган ноқонуний транспорт йўллари глобал тармоғига давлатларнинг жалб этилиши ҳозирги вақтда мамлакатларга гиёхвандлик воситаларни ишлаб чиқарувчилар ва уларнинг истеъмолчиларини аниқ ажратиш имконини бермаяпти. Гиёхвандлик воситаларни турли қитъаларга тарқалишининг маълум тенденцияларини кузатиш ва уларни таҳлил қилишгина мумкин.

Калит сўзлар: Европа полиция идораси (Europol), ҳамкорлик, Европа Иттифоқи, уюшган жиноятчилик, халқаро тармоқ, халқаро қонунчиликни амалга ошириш, гиёхванд моддалар савдосини зарарсизлантириш учун халқаро тузилма, халқаро наркотик назорати, халқаро тактик ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш ташкилоти.

РОЛЬ ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО ПОЛИЦЕЙСКОГО ВЕДОМСТВА (ЕВРОПОЛА) В БОРЬБЕ С НЕЗАКОННЫМ ОБОРОТОМ НАРКОТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Международный масштаб незаконного оборота наркотиков и вовлечение все большего количества государств в мировую сеть маршрутов их нелегальной транспортировки не позволяют в настоящее время четко разграничивать страны на производителей наркотических средств и их потребителей. Имеется возможность только проследить определенные тенденции распространения наркобизнеса применительно к различным континентам и проанализировать их. В статье рассмотрены Основные направления, цели и стратегические задачи систем мониторинга и информационных источников Европейского полицейского ведомства - Европола (European Police Office).

Ключевые слова: Европейское полицейское ведомство (Европол), сотрудничество, ЕС, организованная преступность, международная сеть, имплементация международного нормативного правового акта, международная структура по нейтрализации незаконного оборота наркотиков, международный наркоконтроль, международная тактическая правоохранительная организация.

In 1998, the Convention established the Europol Drug Until Unit, whose status was changed to an agency in 2009 and became known as the European Police Office. Today, Europol operates on the basis of the 2016 Regulations of the European Parliament and the Council [1] and is officially known as the EU Law Enforcement Cooperation Agency (hereinafter referred to as Europol).

This Regulation recognizes that serious crimes often cross internal borders and Europol should therefore support and strengthen the activities of Member States and their cooperation in preventing and combating serious crimes that affect two or more Member States.

The fight against organized crime will therefore remain one of Europol's main objectives, as its scale, importance and impact require a common approach between Member States (paragraph 6). Today, Europol is a platform for multilateral cooperation between police, customs, financial, immigration, border protection authorities, and sometimes even special services of EU member states.

This agency conducts operational activities aimed at countering cross-border threats such as terrorism, human trafficking, drug trafficking, cybercrime, technology crimes, sexual exploitation of children, counterfeiting of money and means of payment, economic crime, money laundering, crimes against intellectual property, corruption, illegal trade in human organs and tissues and other forms of serious crimes. The importance of Europol's activities is evidenced by the fact that the powers of this agency are enshrined at the level of the Constitutive Acts of the EU, which is not typical for the status of agencies that are created by the institutions of the European Union.

Thus, the operational activities of Europol include the implementation of criminal intelligence processes, such as the collection, storage, processing, analysis and exchange of information, in particular that transmitted by the authorities of Member States or third countries or their authorities (clause a part 2 Article 88 TFEU). Tasks may also include the coordination, organization and execution of investigative and operational actions carried out jointly with the competent authorities of the Member States or as part of joint investigative teams, and, if necessary, in connection with Eurojust (clause 2 of Article 88 TFEU) [2].

Of course, security architecture in the context of the fight against international organized crime is a multifaceted mechanism that includes a significant number of international structures operating at different levels of cooperation.

Conditionally we can distinguish:

- global level;
- EU level;
- regional
- national level.

Thus, at the global level, it is worth mentioning the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), the International Criminal Police Organization (INTERPOL), the Organization for Security and Cooperation (OSCE) or the Financial Action Task Force (FATF).

At EU level, in addition to Europol, mention should be made of, among others, the Schengen Platform, the European Office for Strengthening Judicial Cooperation (Eurojust), the College of Europe (CEPOL), the European Agency for the Protection of the External Borders of EU Member States (FRONTEX), the European Office for Combating fraud (OLAF), European Situation Center (SITCEN) and the like.

At the level of regional cooperation, there is the American Community of Policing (AMERIPOL), the Baltic Sea Organized Crime Working Group (BSTF-OC) or the Regional Center for Combating Cross-Border Crime, South East European Cooperation Initiative (SECI). The national level includes competent government bodies whose activities are aimed at controlling, combating and combating crime [3].

Europol is central to this security architecture because, at the global level, Europol replicates Interpol's information-sharing competence. At EU level, Europol's responsibilities coincide with FRONTEX in the areas of strategic analysis, the Schengen platform for information exchange and CEPOL for police training.

Duplication of information exchange rights occurs at the regional level, where similar competencies are occupied by the BSTF-OC and SECI. This is very important, since at the national level of EU member states alone there are more than 300 institutions and services involved in the international exchange of criminal information. Therefore, a feature of this agency is the duplication of operational powers with other organizations.

Europol's relationship with national law enforcement agencies, it should be noted that the agency acts as an addition, a subsidiary element to the work of the national level. Europol does not have executive powers and its officials do not have the power to arrest suspects or act without prior authorization from the competent authorities of member states [4].

Any operational actions of Europol must be carried out in connection with and with the consent of the authorities of the Member State or Member States in whose territory they are applied. The application of coercive measures is the exclusive responsibility of the competent national authorities (Part 3 of Article 88 TFEU).

The use of information and intelligence transmitted through Europol's ongoing investigations and joint investigation teams is subject to the same data protection regime as if it had been received in the receiving Member State.

On the other hand, Europol is responsible for carrying out all activities that support these activities, primarily of an informational, analytical and coordinating nature (for example, starting activities simultaneously in different Member States).

Europol's actual operational support mainly involves intelligence assistance, namely information sharing and criminal intelligence analysis.

Europol collects information from member states, processes, analyzes and disseminates it. For this purpose, Europol operates a special computer system that is used by all member states. Intelligence sharing with member states occurs at two levels:

- strategic (crime analysis, threat assessment);
- operational (providing expertise and technical support for current business needs).

Compared to the police services of member states, the agency has only limited powers, such as initiating investigations or the ability to participate in joint investigative teams.

Considering the fact that Europol, as a mechanism for preventing and combating international organized crime, cooperates not only with EU member states, but also with third countries.

On 22 November 2016, the European Parliament adopted a report on the draft Council decision approving the European Police Office (Europol) Agreement on operational and strategic cooperation between Europol (10345/2016 – C8-0267 / 2016–2016 /0811 (CNS)).

The report stated that, according to Europol, the CIS countries are playing an increasingly important role in the fight against organized crime, in particular drug and economic crimes, human trafficking and smuggling, as well as in the fight against mobile (migratory) organized crime groups.

The exchange of information between the CIS and Europol will allow the EU and member states to more effectively prevent and combat terrorism, organized crime and other forms of its manifestation.

In addition to sharing information, this agreement will also create new opportunities for training and preventive measures. The report also noted that the signing of this agreement on operational and strategic cooperation will become the basis for further coordination of strategies and plans regarding criminal areas between the EU and its member countries. In addition, closer cooperation between the EU and its member states is an example of coherence, complementarity and convergence that is also taking place in other areas, such as the mobility of European citizens [5].

The protection of information exchanged by the Parties is governed by the Memorandum of Understanding regarding confidentiality and ensuring the preservation of information concluded between the Parties. Such a Memorandum includes, in particular, provisions for organizing the security system of the Parties, exercises and trainings, verification standards for classified work, an equivalence table, a procedure for processing information with limited access and assessing the security of information.

The exchange of information with limited access is possible only subject to the conclusion of a Memorandum of Understanding between the CIS countries and Europol regarding confidentiality and ensuring the safety of information [6].

Conclusions. The European Union has created a powerful subsidiary mechanism that carries out a high-level assessment of possible threats in order to prevent international organized crime, as well as support and coordination of the operations of the competent authorities of Member States and third countries. The evolution of Europol's legal status is evidence of the continuous improvement of the EU security system. This is the search for new opportunities for using operational powers, improving information exchange channels, unifying training methods and creating advanced organizational forms of cooperation.

ИҚИБОСЛАР. СНОСКИ. REFERENCES.

1. Regulation (EU) 2016/794 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2016 on the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (Europol). URL: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0794&from=en>.
2. Fundamentals of the law of the European Union: normative materials / M.V. Buromensky, T.M. Anakina, T.V. Komarova and others; ed. M.V. Buromensky. St. Petersburg: Pravo, 2018. P. 328.
3. Safjański T. Pozycja Europolu w architekturze bezpieczeństwa. Zeszyty Naukowe AON. № 1(94). 2019. С. 71-89.
4. Law of the European Union (in questions and answers): textbook. / T.V. Komarova and others; per ed. I.V. Yakovyuk. M: Pravo, 2019. P. 178.
5. Report on the draft Council implementing decision approving the conclusion by the European Police Office (Europol) of the Agreement on Operational and Strategic Cooperation between Europol. URL: http://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-8-2016-0342_PL.html.
6. Zelenyak, A., & Kostyukov, S. (2018). Features of the development of architectonics of crowns of bushes as a criterion of decorativeness in green building. World Ecology Journal, 8(3), 1-22. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.25726/NM.2019.99.51.001>

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